

IMPROVEMENT OF THE MECHANISM OF ORGANIZATION OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT IN BUDGETARY ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation The article discusses the improvement of the mechanism of organization of public procurement in budgetary organizations. Public procurement is a structural tool of the budget. Public procurement is literally important in terms of its tasks and functions, creating the necessary conditions for economic development.

Keywords: Public procurement, targeted programs, digital economy, customer.

Public procurement includes a large share of budget expenditures. In the conditions of modernization of the economy, from year to year in Uzbekistan, work on public procurement is carried out mainly through the conclusion of contracts.

Today in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the public procurement system is the basis for the sustainable development of the digital economy, the expansion and strengthening of international economic cooperation, the need for service is widely promoted.

Rationally using the large-scale capabilities of the digital economy, directly influencing the pace and content of development, that is, the state buys the necessary products for the implementation of targeted development programs, such as education, healthcare, defense, culture, sports. At the same time, the state performs the primary task of regulating the economy.

In the context of the transition to the digital economy, public procurement is considered an important issue that needs to be considered first of all when deepening

economic reforms, since they support national producers, small businesses and public organizations.

If we consider the impact of public procurement on the economy, primarily from the domestic economic policy, it is carried out primarily through the system of public procurement of local producers, small and medium-sized businesses. In turn, the support of small business leads to an increase in the efficiency of the national economy, creates demand for competitive products. Public procurement is considered a large part of budget expenditures and creates opportunities for effective, sustainable development of the digital economy while performing certain functions to meet the needs of the state. That is why the interests of the state customer must coincide with the interests of society. At the same time, it is necessary that the organizational structures of public procurement be transparent. Research shows that government contractors may have corrupt incentives to choose one of these mechanisms.

According to the analysis of public procurement in many countries, the choice of the type of procurement is influenced by the expected number of government customers, procurement participants, the complexity of the government contract and the level of political competition. For example, if a customer wants to buy a complex product or service, it will be more useful for him to negotiate than an auction, that is, it depends on the choice of the type of procurement procedure. Choosing a winner based on several indicators gives more opportunities to limit competition than an auction based on one indicator. In multidimensional auctions, participants compete on a number of parameters, such as price and delivery time. Performance points are accumulated in certain promotions, and the bidder with the highest number of points becomes the winner of the auction.

For the month of April 2021 through a special information portal on public procurement of JSC "UzRTSB" - xarid.uz concluded deals worth 734.0 billion soums, which is 20.2% more than last month. The total amount of savings of budget organizations and enterprises with a state share amounted to about 138.5 billion soums .

Fig.1. Dynamics of the volume of concluded transactions on electronic public procurement in January- April 2021.

For the month of April of this year, budget customers concluded transactions worth over 313.9 billion soums, and corporate customers concluded in electronic form in the amount of 420.1 billion soums.

In particular, the total volume of transactions in the electronic store amounted to over 261.3 billion soums, and through an electronic auction – over 324.6 billion soums. At the same time, the volume of transactions concluded in the electronic tender amounted to 148.1 billion soums.

The method of deception at the auction on the part of the customer can also lead to unequal consequences. There is a possibility of reducing economic efficiency while creating broad corruption opportunities for the customer.

The customer may also restrict the participation of companies in competitive procurement procedures by making excessive demands on the procurement participants and manipulating the terms of the contract.

The possibilities of using the above methods and combining them will depend on the selected procurement procedures.

The first way to limit competition is to make excessive demands on the procurement participants and use tricks with the terms of the contract. By making excessive demands on bidders and falsifying the terms of the contract, only one company or a narrow circle of companies can fulfill the state contract by offering bribes. In order to make the public procurement management system transparent for both the State and society, it is desirable to introduce a monitoring system and to continuously collect, summarize, systematize and evaluate information about procurement, including the creation of a monitoring system that ensures the implementation of procurement plans and schedules.

In the field of public procurement, anti-corruption monitoring should be considered as a mechanism to improve the efficiency of economic management, it is reflected in the risks in the contract system in order to analyze the situation and ensure transparency of public procurement.

The main components of anti-corruption monitoring are:

- identification of monitoring objects, i.e. manifestations of corruption on the part of clients and potential performers in accordance with anti-corruption legislation in the public procurement system;
- identification of factors and sources of corruption;
- formation of a number of reliable data about objects, including data collection, public procurement;
- analysis of public procurement information as a processing process;
- to determine the level of transparency of public procurement and assess the damage caused by corruption as a process of determining the following types:
 - a) financial losses caused by price increases for the state and society;
 - b) quantitative damage in cases of overestimation or understatement of the delivered products (works, services) or improper acquisition;
 - v) damage caused during the conclusion of transactions with violation of the necessary technical conditions, quality and reliability parameters;

d) political damage in the conclusion of agreements related to the restriction of competition and, accordingly, the loss of confidence in state institutions in society and business.

- forecasting as a process of determining the future impact of corruption factors and developing directions for the development of anti-corruption policy in the field of regulation and regulation of public procurement.

Therefore, an integral element of the anti-corruption monitoring system in the public procurement system is monitoring based on the collection and analysis of statistical data on the procurement process. At the same time, it is impossible to analyze the state and development of the public procurement system in time and space (statistical analysis), i.e. it is impossible to present indicators without the parameters of the object of study. In addition, the above-mentioned features of public procurement, undoubtedly, due to certain indicators, complexity and dynamics of procurement, cannot comprehensively and in detail reflect the social phenomenon under consideration. In order to carry out anti-corruption monitoring, it is necessary to assess the manifestations of corruption. To achieve this goal, there is still cooperation in the field of public procurement, unification and a system of indicators that have not reached the level of universal scientific and practical recognition are needed. Therefore, as one of the goals of this study, the task of developing a system of indicators in the system of ensuring transparency of public procurement was identified.

Public procurement indicators

Organizational Indicators	Key	Organizational Key Indicators
Public procurement		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the number of purchases made in violation of the terms of publication of notices and reports on public procurement; - the number of procedures with violations in the total number of declared procedures; - the number of contracts for which the fine was not applied; - the number of terminated contracts unilaterally compared to the number of contracts concluded on his initiative, etc.
Volume of public procurement		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the volume of purchases from one supplier; - the volume of purchases from small businesses; - the volume of purchases made using electronic platforms; - the absolute amount of saved purchases, etc.

Structure of public procurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - distribution of samples depending on whether they are open or closed; - restriction of choice and gradual distribution; - share of the closed auction; - the share of electronic auctions. - the share of centralized purchases; - share of joint purchases; - the share of purchases from one supplier, etc.
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A source: Prepared by the author

Regular growth of state budget revenues allows increasing the share of its expenditures. Therefore, solving the problem of ensuring effective spending of budget funds, the formation and placement of government orders, and improving their organizational and managerial efficiency remains an important issue in the transition to the digital economy.

The transition to improving the efficiency of public procurement is an important task of forming a market mechanism for ensuring government orders. Public procurement is carried out on the basis of government orders formed based on the needs of the state.

The experience of foreign countries shows that public procurement occupies a large part of the budget, while it is an important factor in economic management.

That is why today, as in many countries of the world, much attention is paid to the integration of the public procurement system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In order to ensure openness, transparency and efficiency of procurement processes, the state is implementing a number of measures to strengthen competition at auctions through the use of electronic bidding and the involvement of business entities in the public procurement process. At this point, it is important in what order the purchases of the dalat are made.

It should be noted that in the past period in our country, based on international experience and the requirements of economic reforms, efforts were made to form a unique system for organizing public procurement, that is, the effective use of budget funds, providing more benefits. for small and medium-sized businesses in the procurement process, in addition, the public procurement system is focused on the possibilities of organizing the existing mechanism in accordance with international

standards. Undoubtedly, the development of modern forms and procedures in the public procurement system is becoming a vital necessity. The improvement of public procurement depends on the creation of a perfect regulatory framework for this sphere and its development in accordance with international experience, since the regulatory framework creates the basis for the formation of a mechanism for any sphere.

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